

IOT-BASED MEDICAL EMERGENCY DETECTION DEVICE

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Abstract. The study aims to create and construct a safety monitoring system for people with medical conditionals that will benefit their families. It should stay updated on their conditional and health to avoid anything horrible. The device was created and developed to help those persons with disabilities and persons with medical conditions to be monitored using the project, mostly those persons who are no longer being monitored because of lack of finances and lack of attention from their family members or relatives. The device's priorities are the persons with a medical condition and the person with a disability – their vital signs such as body temperature, pulse rate, and blood oxygen. The system gives ease and helps the users have a proper monitoring device and notify their family members.

Keywords. Medical Emergency, Internet of Things, Detection Devices

1 Introduction

One of the main problems for adult people like senior citizens is keeping their balance while walking, especially for stroke history. It is getting more challenging to move, and if they fall, it isn't effortless to get back up. Besides, most older adults don't have the energy to shout or call for help when there is urgency. There is some emergency detection that can help, but for now, we don't have it here in the Philippines. Emergencies can happen to anyone, but the adult is especially susceptible to those incidents he short-term and long-term effects. It isn't always feasible for a caregiver to be with a medical condition at the least time to guard them against accidents (jean parcel).

A wearable emergency detection device for the medical condition individuals is the following neatest thing to make sure your beloved has access to emergency help round the clock. With medical Conditions are predisposed to isolation due to declining physical mobility and health problems. Spending too much time alone inevitably leads to loneliness and puts older people at risk of being isolated and unable to seek assistance during medical emergencies. As a citizenry, it's only natural to wish for a unique place to call our own. One's mental and emotional well-being needs to live independently and control one day-to-day life. Moving to home comes with advantages, but losing control over many aspects of lifestyle paired with reduced family contact causes devastating emotional consequences. It is also a posh process for a home resident to partake in activities outside the home. Thus, it's best to undertake to take care of autonomy and live independently or in assisted living for as long as possible. For older people, an alarm button is an option that allows them to measure safely and independently in their own homes. Having a medical condition loved one is often problematic, thanks to all of the age-related risks they face. Stress and worries over loved ones are often to your health. Lowering your loved ones' risk may be a great way to realize peace of mind. An emergency button for medical condition relations can make their lives safe and reduce their worries. A medical alert device makes it straightforward to urge for help immediately with the press of a button. It can help in other situations than only an attack or fall. Subscribers can push their control if they feel sick, have chest pains, hear someone breaking into their home, have a fireplace, or the other emergency. There is no need to speak to get help – one only has to press a button. An emergency button for medical conditions may be a lifeline once they need it most. Knowing your family has access to such a service can bring great comfort and peace of mind to you and your loved ones.

In this time of the pandemic, once you have the symptoms of COVID-19, you will automatically be isolated in the house or, worse, in the hospital alone. The researcher strongly believes that this prototype will help, especially when you have to be alone to recover and not infect others, especially your family members. This prototype will help you connect with your family members when you seek help or urgency from the medical personnel. More than 11 million with medical conditions live alone, and smaller family sizes equate to increasing isolation as we age. Nearly percent of the medical condition spend their sunset years in nursing homes/homes for the agent. As we get older, maintaining our freedom becomes a matter of protection, finances, and the ability to meet basic human needs. An emergency detection device for old age individuals can extend their time spent independently. Because of the monitoring and alerting capabilities, living

accommodations are possible. Emergency detection devices ensure trained professionals are on-call 24/7 to help in an emergency. If the crisis is wellbeing-related, utilizing a crisis catch can interface your cherished one to an expert who can organize crisis help right away. This prototype is, as of now, gathered in different nations. However, the researcher is bringing it here in the Philippines and improving it by adding the individual's crucial indications wearing this prototype.

Up to the present time, the researcher is thinking about how to improve the emergency button and add more features to this prototype, like adding a pulse rate, and temperature to monitor the vital signs. This patient's family can watch even if they are not in their house. Medical emergency detection devices keep up only care costs that the old on a tight spending plan can manage. Everybody needs a lifesaver at their most earnest critical crossroads. Fortunately, numerous choices are open to you and your family. Investigating surveys and correlations can help you discover the option with the best highlights for your adored one, which will give them the well-being and solace they need in their brilliant years (Wanhong Wu).

The researcher's motivation in doing this prototype, light and comfortable to wear the device, especially for medical conditions, stroke and cancer patients and children with special needs and caregivers and family members, is to help them improve their daily living.

2 Review of Related Literature

The rapid growth of the medical condition population has resulted in an immense increase in demand for health services. Eventually, the medical condition is more prone to health problems than other age groups (Wang et al., 2017). In the year 2018, According to the research Duarte wearable fitness devices (WHDs) are increasingly helping people better monitor their health status both at an activity/fitness level for self-health monitoring and at the medical level that provides more there is a lot of data in clinics with potential for earlier diagnosis and treatment guidance. The technological revolution in the miniaturization of electronic devices allows the design of more reliable and adaptable wearables, contributing to a worldwide innovation in health monitoring. This research examines the essential aspects of WHDs, which are listed in the state-of-the-art wearable critical sensing hallmarks technologies and their architecture and system specifications. (Dias & Cunha, 2018).

The work of (Napi et al., 2019) says that the remote health monitoring system that the medical institution was seriously facing problems as part of the medical condition population that is increasing due to a lack of doctors. The level of physical activity for older adults with intellectual disabilities (ID) is exceptionally low, and their health levels are equivalent to vulnerable older people and well below-agreed averages for older people with average intelligence (Echteld, 2016

Hypertension is a common issue in the medical condition, and blood pressure (BP) targets are also disputed, with BP monitoring thresholds lower in this population of patients (Mihailescu et al., 2019). Since you normally don't see any signs when your blood pressure is quietly causing harm to your body, high blood pressure is referred to as the silent killer. However, often high blood pressure surges to dangerously high levels, posing an acute, severe, and potentially life-threatening threat (Lorna Collier, 2021).

Common in adults 65 and older are limited from doing activities or exercises and they are the most prone to cardiovascular disease, hypertension, and hypoxemia which affects the heart, blood vessels, or both, is more. Changes in the heart and blood vessels associated with aging may raise a person's risk of cardiovascular disease. With the help of this study, the heart rate of an elder person will be monitored anytime. Since it predicts signs of heart attacks and other cardiac complications, an IoT-Based medical emergency detection device is ideal for preventing cardiovascular disease. This system can continuously track blood oxygen levels with some specificity and may aid in the detection of symptoms for conditions such as sleep apnea. When seniors need emergency assistance, IoT-Based medical emergency detection device is there for them. It has an alarm button that can be pressed or automatically alarm at any moment, alerting your loved ones or relatives.

Accordingly, further investigation into the potential of adaptive alarms for continuous vital symptom monitoring in ward patients is provided. A classical threshold-based alarm approach was for constant vital signs monitoring in surgical ward patients—combinations of simulated six methods to adjust alarm thresholds to personal or situational factors in the same dataset. Caution execution was surveyed utilizing the general alert rate and affectability to decide antagonistic occasions.

Plans that fit critical alarm thresholds in signaling personal or situational factors can improve early detection of adverse events or reduce alarm rates to classical alarm (van Rossum et al., 2021).

Watching medical conditions is one of the promising IoT applications in nursing care. Emergency medical equipment is considered to be an essential agent for not only relaxing medical conditions but also watching and alerting them in daily life. Detecting and avoiding the risk of internal heatstroke is a critical issue, especially for seniors living alone. A methodology for reliably transmitting the possible risk of internal heatstroke with a medical condition is essential for implementing a practical system. The proposed system implements a proper notification of abnormal conditions in the medical condition through an emergency medical device (Yatsuda et al., 2019).

This method allows data from different sources to be combined to better assess the patient's health status and identify possible anticipatory actions. One unique possible solution to overcome these limitations is the interconnection of medical devices via the Internet using a distributed platform, particularly the IoT. Such data is sometimes stored in spreadsheets, does not form part of patients' electronic health records, and is difficult for caregivers to integrate and analyze (da Costa et al., 2018). It says the design of a real-time health monitoring system can store a patient's primary health parameters. The data can be made available to a medical practitioner as an alert and monitored through multiple communication means. At present, healthcare systems exist with single-mode communication options - popularly either in GSM or data access. With their research, healthcare delivery by communicating multiplexed data over three modes-BLE (mobile application), GSM (messaging services), and Wi-Fi (Internet) (Swaroop et al., 2019).

The targets of this study were to develop and evaluate the effectiveness of an emergency device for the elderly and individuals with disabilities through usability testing. This study has two phases: one development of a prototype for an emergency alert device and two ease of use testing. Results presented improvement of the prototype, which comprised parts for sending and receiving notifications. There are two kinds of alarms for emergency notification: conscious and unconscious alerts. It consists of two phases: (1) developing a prototype for improving an emergency alert device and (2) ease of use testing of the device for older people and people with disabilities in the community. The device was designed in the first stage from the literature review and analysis of similar devices recently placed on the market (Tayeh et al., 2020).

The analysis points from the literature review and analysis of recent alert devices in the Thai market [7-9] are the overall device appearance, functions, and usability of older people and people with disabilities Community. In general appearance, this study found that most alert devices have at least two components: signals transmitting the component and receiving the call. Some transmission parts are designed with a wrist or like a watch or message watch, but others are intended as a box fixed to the wall. However, all designs have an SOS button. Most of the received components are designed as an alarm box with an alarm sound, but some have sounds and real-time video calls (Lersilp et al., 2020). MCP9808 digital temperature sensor converts between -40°C and $+125^{\circ}\text{C}$ into a digital word with an accuracy of $\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ (max.). The MCP9808 includes user-programmable registers that provide flexibility for temperature-sensing applications. The logs allow user-selectable settings such as Shutdown or low-power mode. The temperature detail and fundamental yield limits, when the temperature changes past the predetermined edge limits and the MCP9808, emit an Event signal (Cho et al., 2020).

Continuous monitoring generally imposes a range of barriers, including form factor, energy consumption, and motion support to empower any place and whenever observing. Inside this unique situation, sensors assume a significant part as the principal building square of such frameworks and the primary section point for the checking cycle. In this manner, to experiment with continuous health monitoring systems in similar conditions, sensing platforms need to meet several relevant requirements and constraints, especially mobility. This section plans to introduce an outline of popular sensing platforms that meet appropriate restrictions, allowing experiments and researchers to initiate prototyping and experimental projects for continuous health monitoring. The sensing platforms were classified into three proposed and compared categories, namely, ready-to-use, and ready-to-build kits.

Wearable smart sensors are arising technology for daily monitoring of vital signs, reducing discomfort and disrupting everyday human activities. The main objective of this study was to evaluate applied wearable smart sensors for disease control and essential monitoring of signs in outbreaks of epidemics. Most sensors monitor body temperature, heart rate,

fall detection, blood oxygen (SpO₂), and notification. Wearable devices (such as a helmet, watch, or cuff) and body area network sensors are popular types that can be used to monitor vital signs for epidemic trends. Applying appropriate technological solutions can improve disease epidemic control and management and use sensors for continuous monitoring of vital signs. However, further consideration is needed to investigate the actual effects of these sensors and their effectiveness (Mohammadzadeh et al., 2020). In these situations, short-term monitoring of patients helps the medical team take the necessary steps without delay. Patient monitoring reveals threatening events to caregivers, and most such systems use physiological input data for direct control of support tools (Baskar et al., 2020). However, considering current global conditions, smart wearable sensors for monitoring patients have the capacity and potential to be a significant breakthrough in efforts to control epidemics. The framework is responsible for observing decision-making and maintaining the functions and operating times of wearable sensors (WS) as a part of healthcare monitoring applications. In this framework, the nature of the remote detecting gadget and its characteristic features are considered to design a fully operational and automatic seamless working of sensing devices. Sensing devices operate in both autonomous and coherent ways depending on the sensed information and the experimental conditions of the patient's body. The frequency of operation and time interval varies with the scheduled and random recommendations of the communication framework of the coherent devices. The framework is planned to improve the interoperability of devices that have been acclimatized to adapt to the dynamic nature of different healthcare applications to utilize their performance (Baskar et al., 2020).

3 Project Design and Methodology

To create a medical emergency, the proponents need to collect the data and requirements required for the proposed study. The researcher needs to know the patient's health status and a person with disabilities, the prototype used for medical emergencies for their safety, and a kind of emergency alert system that will be a way to know the situation of our families. It is a project for people who do not have time to monitor the condition of their families at home. This project is for people who need it and are in a state of emergency to prevent any incident.

The proponent's materials are of great importance, especially to the medical condition and the person with disabilities (PWD). If the crisis is wellbeing-related, utilizing a crisis catch can interface your cherished one to an expert who can organize crisis help right away.

Figure 1. Operational Framework for the Proposed Project

The device is built with a pulse beat sensor that will detect the patient's pulse rate whether it is normal or not, and the infrared thermometer will see the patient's temperature for a standard range of 36°C to 37.2°C. While the accelerometer will be the one for determining the position of the patient, if the patient gets into a situation where he /she falls, the sensor will be triggered. The SMS module will act as sending information from patients to their relatives through SMS text. All data will be stored as an SMS message on the smartphone or the specific application.

4 Results and Discussion

Figure 2 shows the schematic diagram of that wireframe containing wirings of the project's modules and sensors to the system's brain, which modules and sensors are the body temperature scanner module, MAX30102 sensor, LCD, heart rate scanner, mmpu-6050 with the MH-ET LIVE MiniKit for ESP32 has built-in Wi-Fi, which is required for data transmission as well as data to the mobile application, and the most pin of LCD is connected to pin 23 of the ESP32, sclk connected to pin 18, is connected to pin 5, dc connected to pin 26, reset pin connected to pin 33 and the bl connected to pin 0. While the max30102 will detect the blood oxygen and temperature of the user, the scl pin is connected to pin 21 of the ESP32 module, sda is connected to pin 22, the positive which is vcc connected to 5v of the module, and the ground connected to the ground of the module. For detecting the heart rate of the user, the sensor's signal pin is connected to the svp pin, vcc to positive, and negative to the ground. For detecting the accelerometer, the proponents used the mmpu-6050 that will detect the motion of the user, where the scl pin is connected to pin 21, sda to pin 22, and the vcc is connected to the positive, and ground to the negative. the proponents used the sims800L that will send the data for the notification alert to the mobile application. where the rst pin is connected to pin16, RXD to pin 17, and the TXD pin is to pin 19, the positive which is vcc connected to 5v of the module, and the ground is connected to the ground of the module.

Figure 2. Schematic Diagram-Based Medical Emergency Detection Device

The MH-ET LIVE MiniKit for ESP32 makes up the hardware portion of the project. This is an open-source platform based on ESP32, which is a series of low-cost, low-power system-on-a-chip microcontrollers with built-in Wi-Fi and dual-mode Bluetooth. It is built around the microprocessor, which combines WiFi, Bluetooth, Ethernet, and low-power functionality into a single chip. This would be advantageous. carry the codes and programs for the sensors and modules so that they can work as required. To complete the configuration of all modules and sensors, first, most pins of lcd have pins which are the sclk connected to pin 18, connected to pin 5, DC connected to pin 26, reset pin connected to pin 33, and the bl connected to pin 0. The scl pin is attached to pin 21 of the ESP32 module, the sda pin is connected to pin 22, the positive is vcc connected to 5v of the module, and the ground is connected to the ground of the module in the max30102 will monitor the user's blood oxygen and temperature. The sensor's signal pin is linked to the svp pin, vcc to positive, and negative to

ground to measure the user's heart rate. The proponents employed the mmpu-6050 to detect the accelerometer, which will detect the user's motion when the SCL pin is attached to it.

The project has a motion detector, the proponents used MPU 6050 which will detect the motion of the patient or the accelerometer part of the project. The SCL pin of the sensor is connected to pin 21 of the microcontroller while the SDA pin is connected to pin 22. For the power supply, the vcc pin is connected to the positive of the ESP32 and ground.

Figure 3. MH-ET LIVE MiniKit for ESP32 with max30102

For detecting the blood oxygen of the patient, the proponents used the max30102 sensor which will detect the blood oxygen of the person using the project at the same time his temperature. The SCL pin of the sensor is connected to pin 21 of the ESP32 module while SDA is connected to pin 22. In supplying power to the sensor, the vcc pin is connected to the 5v of the ESP32 while the ground pin is connected to the ground of the module.

Figure 4. MH-ET LIVE MiniKit for ESP32 with Heartrate Scanner

In developing the hardware part of the project, the proponents connect the LCD to the microcontroller which is the ESP32. Upon connecting the wires of the LCD to ESP32, the most pin of the LCD is connected to pin 23 of the microcontroller. The SCLK is connected to pin 18 while the CS pin is connected to pin 5. The DC pin is connected to pin 26 while the rest pin of the LCD is connected to pin 33 and lastly, the BL pin is connected to pin.

For the notification alert system, the proponents used the module sims800L for sending the data as the emergency notification alert to mobile application users. The proponents connect the sim800L to the microcontroller which is the ESP32. Once the wires from the Sims800L are connected to the ESP32, the rst pin is connected to pin16, the rxd to pin 17, and the txd pin to pin 19, the positive which is the vcc connected to 5v of the module, and ground connected to the ground of the module.

The proponent's design for the prototype was put into an actual medical detecting devices prototype after attaching the modules and sensors to the microcontroller. The proponents used 3D printing of the medical device prototype box. It will be fitted with sensors and modules. The proponents encountered some problems during the printing of the enclosure of the project, incorrect size of the enclosure, and the 3D printer not working properly that's why the proponents need to start printing again.

Figure 5 shows the actual model of a Medical Detection Devices prototype. All sensors are connected to the microcontroller at the same time, the LCD is also connected to display the temperature, heart rate per minute, and blood oxygen of people with medical conditions which are the vital signs of humans.

Figure 5. Actual Model of Medical Detection Device Prototype

Table 1 shows the matrix of the combination and criteria of the heart's beat per minute, blood oxygen, and temperature of the user of the project to determine if the system should perform the emergency function where it will send a notification to the family members. The table shows the normal heartbeats per minute of 60 to 100 BPM, blood oxygen with 95% to 100%, and temperature of 36 to 37.2 degrees Celsius.

Table 1. Combination and Criteria for Emergency Trigger

BEATS PER MINUTE	59	60	59	59	60	60	59	60-100 NORMAL
BLOOD OXYGEN	90%	90%	95%	90%	95%	90%	95%	95% - 100% NORMAL
TEMPERATURE	37.8	37.8	37.8	36	37.8	36	36	36 - 37.2 NORMAL
EMERGENCY ALARM	TRUE	FALSE						

To be able to connect the Blynk app to Arduino, The Blynk app will receive the data from the microcontroller which are the body temperature, blood oxygen, and heart rate per minute. For every change in data, that is different from the set data in the Arduino, the Arduino will send.

Figure 6. Design for Bridge Example Device Set-Up

Figure 6 shows a wireframe to display the results within the buttons the textbox button shows the sample for the normal and abnormal vital signs of someone with medical conditions using the mobile app and device connection.

Wireframe Design for the monitor of connection to the mobile app and the hardware. It includes the configuration of connection to Wi-Fi notification sounds and vibration for the devices connected.

Figure 7. Design for Activate Notification of the Device

Upon testing the project, the proponents encountered some problems where the heart rate, blood oxygen, and temperature did not give accurate measures so the proponents did some calibration and compared it to other devices existing to determine if the vital signs were correct.

The other problem that the proponents encountered was notification. When the vital signs do not meet the required combination of each vital sign the emergency notification will start to send a notification to the family member but the problem is, even if the family member is already with the patient, the notification won't stop sending. So, the proponents decided to add a manual button on the device where it will be pressed once if the family member is with the patient already to stop sending notifications. For other functions, if the patient needs help, they can manually press the button for two seconds to send a notification that they need help. Then if the patient wants to call a family member, the patient will just need to press the button for ten seconds to do a call.

Figure 8. Arduino Project Testing Through Serial Monitor

Plate 12 shows the Arduino IDE's serial monitor which displays the data that is being scanned by the temperature, blood oxygen, heart rate per minute, and the motion of the user. This test shows that every data being scanned and sent to the application is showing here in the serial monitor.

The proponents tested the project and every time that the data being scanned will change from normal to above normal or below normal, the notification will be sent to the application where the family members of the user can monitor the patient or the user. It shows "fall detected" when the motion of the patient changes accidentally and "need help" when the person's vital signs change to above or below normal. There is also a notification when the patient manually presses the manual button to send a notification to his or her family members.

The proponents discussed the project with the user at the same time, the proponents were given a demonstration on how to use it and how it works. Figure 9 shows that the user or the patient was given a survey questionnaire for them to fill

up and evaluate the project. The evaluation of the users will help the proponents to determine the project's effectiveness and usability. The users experience that the system is sometimes not giving an accurate value of the vitals signs because some sensors are having problems which is why they were answering the "neither agree nor disagree" column.

Figure 9. User While Testing Evaluating the Project

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

IoT-based medical emergency detection device helps those persons with a medical condition and those persons with disabilities to monitor their vital signs and their safety. One of the main problems in this aspect is those people with medical conditions and persons with disabilities are no longer given any attention and are being neglected by their family members because of having their own lives or family and children or relatives of the patient.

The proponents conclude that the body temperature does not give an accurate value of temperature, it senses the body temperature of the user but sometimes it senses the surrounding temperature. So, the proponents did some calibration and compared it to other body temperature scanners to determine if the sensor would give an accurate temperature.

The proponents conclude that the project must have the right combination of blood oxygen, body temperature, and pulse rate. The proponents did some web browsing to search what are the normal vital signs and also, and they also interviewed some nurses to have proof that this combination is the normal measure of the blood oxygen, temperature, and pulse rate so that the system's sending notifications will be set if the vital signs are not in a normal range. In terms of notification, proponents also concluded that a manual button must be present in the physical prototype because sometimes, the user has a normal vital sign but they were already in danger.

The proponent's recommendation to the user of the IoT-based medical emergency detection is to always have a regular load instead of unlimited so the load from the sim won't expire and will only be used as long as the changes in the vital signs occur. The future researcher who will do research and study related to this study can add more features to this project. The case or enclosure of the main project can have a smaller case and a good strap on the wrist so it will be more comfortable in terms of usability and comfortability.

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